

ISSUES OF SYSTEMATIZING NORMATIVE LEGAL ACTS IN THE RESOLUTION OF LEGAL COLLISIONS

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the role of systematizing and harmonizing legislation in resolving legal conflicts. It identifies the causes of duplication, contradictions, and inconsistencies arising in the legislative process and outlines effective methods of systematization to eliminate them. The paper focuses on the concepts of codification and consolidation, emphasizing their importance in resolving conflicts between legal documents.*

Keywords: *legal conflict, harmonization, codification, consolidation, lawmaking, systematization methods, legal norms, legal order.*

Introduction. It is known that the lawmaker, in the process of creating, amending, and supplementing certain normative legal acts, tries to thoroughly analyze the existing legal framework and avoid certain duplications, inconsistencies, and contradictions. However, no matter how much activity in this area is carried out taking into account the above aspects, it is impossible to fully achieve the prevention and resolution of possible conflicts in legislation. In this regard, it should be noted that the systematization and consolidation of legislation, which is one of the important methods of the mechanism for resolving legal conflicts, is of particular importance in solving problems in this area.

Although issues related to the systematization and harmonization of legislation have been studied to a certain extent by domestic and foreign legal scholars, they do not dwell in detail on the role and significance of these methods in resolving legal conflicts. It should be noted that, like other types of creativity, lawmaking is constantly developing in accordance with the processes taking place in society. After all, the emergence of social relations that should be regulated by legal norms requires constant activity from the lawmaker, the creation of new regulatory legal acts, and the introduction of amendments and additions to existing ones. This, in turn, leads to regular changes in the scope of normative legal acts and, in most cases, to their expansion in volume and the emergence of certain contradictions between them. The solution to these problems requires the systematization of legislation.

In this regard, as the legal scholar U.Kh. Mukhamedov rightly acknowledges, "the importance of taking into account normative legal acts is clearly visible in cases of a significant increase in the number of legislative acts, the emergence of mutual contradictions in legislative acts, their duplication, and violations of legislative procedures [1]".

Methodology. Systematization of legislation is an activity carried out to regulate and improve legislation, which provides for bringing these documents into a defined and internally interconnected system. In this regard, we consider it appropriate to dwell on the approaches to the purpose of systematizing legislation in legal sciences and its significance in resolving contradictions in legislation.

In particular, according to legal scholars M.K.Najimov and Sh.A.Saydullayev, the systematization of normative legal acts is carried out for the following purposes: development and

further improvement of legislation; correct understanding and application of normative acts; facilitation of finding the necessary normative act (norm); elimination of contradictions, ambiguities, duplications, gaps in current legislation; formation of legal consciousness and culture of subjects of legal relations [2].

As noted above, during the development of the legal system, after a certain period, the volume of normative legal acts with the same subject of regulation increases. This, along with the repetition of the provisions of these documents, also leads to the emergence of conflicts in them. In such cases, by consolidating normative legal acts, it is possible to eliminate contradictions in them.

As we familiarize ourselves with the legal literature on the topic, we see that certain approaches to the concept of consolidation have been put forward in them. Since these approaches are mainly close to each other, we will limit ourselves to citing the following opinions of legal scholars M.K. Najimov and Sh.A. Saydullayev regarding this concept: "consolidation is a form of systematization in which no changes are made to the content of normative legal acts, but these norms lose their force as an independent legal act. Consolidation is an intermediate form of systematization of normative legal acts between incorporation and codification.

As a result of consolidation, normative legal acts of different legal force regulating one type of social relations are summarized, and on this basis, unnecessary duplication and contradictions are eliminated [3].

Indeed, in the process of preparing a consolidated document, the norms of previously effective normative legal acts are placed in a logical sequence, and the general structure of the document being created is developed. In order to present it in a unified style and unify the relevant terms, it is edited to a certain extent. Also, normative legal acts are excluded from collisions, repetitions, unreasonably long sentences, outdated terms are eliminated, and norms that are close to each other in terms of content are combined into one article or chapter. In turn, a new normative legal act created on the basis of consolidation, covering the norms of previous acts included in its composition, will have its official details as an independent document, that is, its name, time of adoption, serial number, and signature of the relevant official. All this testifies to the fact that consolidation manifests itself as a form of law-making activity of state bodies.

The codification form of systematization of normative legal acts also plays an important role in resolving conflicts in legislation.

Codification is the systematization of normative acts into a single normative act on a logical basis by changing their content. In the process of codification, outdated norms are eliminated, contradictions in the entire legal system are eliminated, and legal gaps are filled.

According to the Russian legal scholar V.N. Protasov, codification, as an important form of systematization of normative legal acts, is distinguished by the following features:

firstly, the activity of codification is carried out only by the subject of lawmaking (parliament);

secondly, as a result of codification, a new normative legal act is created, containing norms that differ significantly from those previously in effect;

thirdly, the document being codified is a consolidated document. Because in it, the norms previously reflected in various documents, but which served to regulate a certain sphere of social relations, are concentrated in one place;

fourthly, the codified act is the main one among the acts in force in a certain sphere of social relations;

fifthly, the normative legal acts created as a result of codification are designed to regulate social relations for a long time. Taking into account possible changes in social life, they will have the ability to regulate further improved social relations that will arise in the future [4].

Over the past thirty years of our country's independence, the codification of regulatory legal acts in various spheres of social reality has been carried out in stages with the emergence of objective conditions. Proposals and recommendations developed by legal science will help the legislator understand the need for codification of normative legal acts in a particular field. In this regard, it is natural that various debates arise among the scientific community regarding the codification of a particular field. Considering the current situation in certain areas of our national legal system, in particular in the spheres of electoral and environmental law, many legal scholars and practicing specialists are proposing the creation of a unified codified document based on the unification of regulatory legal acts in these areas. In particular, Kh.T. Odilkoriev and Sh.U. Yakubov put forward the following opinion on the systematization of electoral legislation: "Considering that more than ten laws regulating electoral relations have been adopted in the Republic of Uzbekistan, their systematization as a single code creates certain conveniences for our citizens and helps in obtaining information about electoral processes. Currently, there are 10 laws and about 260 articles directly related to the electoral process in force in the Republic of Uzbekistan. If these laws are systematized into a single code and analogous norms are eliminated, this branch of legislation will be unified [5]".

In the field of ecology, a number of legal scholars are putting forward proposals for the adoption of a code. In particular, Sh.Kh. Fayziev, M.B. Usmanov, Yu.O. Zhuraev, Zh.T. Kholmuminov, N.R. Akhmanov, Zh.I. Safarov note that the time has come to implement a reform of legislation on environmental protection and rational use, that is, it is necessary to bring environmental legislation into the form of a code. In addition to the methods of systematization of regulatory legal acts analyzed above, there is also the method of incorporation. In this form of systematization, a new normative legal act is not created. However, through this method, it is possible to identify conflicts in legislation, that is, in the process of systematizing normative legal acts regulating certain social relations on a thematic basis, duplications and contradictory situations in them are identified. However, conflicts in legislation cannot be resolved in this case. This can only be achieved through codification and consolidation methods of systematization.

Recognizing that our national legislation is developing on the basis of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, norms of international law, and generally recognized principles, it is also necessary to improve it in accordance with the characteristics of socio-economic development and adopt new regulatory legal acts. In this regard, it is worth noting the following thoughts of legal scholar Sh.Kh. Fayziev: "As our society develops, the objective need to strengthen its legal foundations, critically review existing legislative acts, make additions and amendments based on today's requirements, cancel old laws that do not meet modern requirements and create new ones, as well as improve the quality of legislative acts will continue to grow [6]".

It should be noted that the current legislation establishes a detailed procedure for the preparation and adoption of normative legal acts, including the preparation and discussion of draft laws, their adoption, publication, entry into force, as well as issues related to the types of normative legal acts, their legal status, interaction, and the resolution of possible conflicts (collisions) between them. In particular, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Normative Legal Acts" (new edition), the Constitutional Law "On the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan," the Constitutional Law "On the

Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan," the Law "On the Procedure for Preparing Draft Laws and Submitting them to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan," the Law "On the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan," the Law "On Electronic Document Management," the Resolution of the Council of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Methodological Recommendations for the Legal and Technical Formatting of Draft Laws."

Results and discussion. As can be seen from the foregoing, special attention is paid in our country to the creation of a legal basis for mechanisms for preventing and resolving conflicts in legislation. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan plays an important role in preventing and resolving legal conflicts. The third chapter of our Basic Law is called "The Supremacy of the Constitution and Law," and Article 15 of it states that "The supremacy of the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan is recognized unconditionally in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The state, its bodies, officials, public associations, and citizens act in accordance with the Constitution and laws [7]"

Article 16 of the Constitution strictly establishes that no provision of this Constitution may be interpreted in a way that harms the rights and interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and no law or other normative legal act may contradict the norms and provisions of the Constitution. Therefore, the Constitution - an official document - is the foundation and basis of any democratic society, state, and governance. Therefore, the supremacy of the Constitution and law is among the fundamental principles of a state governed by the rule of law. The Constitution and laws are considered one of the most important features of statehood.

Along with the constitutional foundations for the prevention and resolution of legislative conflicts, certain provisions are also established in the aforementioned regulatory legal acts. Considering that a detailed analysis of their content is much wider than the scope and possibilities of this brochure, we consider it expedient to consider the issues of improving the legal framework in this area. Indeed, the important reforms carried out in recent years in the sphere of state and law, especially the recent parliamentary reforms, have changed the process of lawmaking, including lawmaking. In this regard, they must also find their appropriate expression in the legal foundations of the legislative process. In the scientific and legal literature of our country, there are recognizable opinions on the need for further improvement of the legal foundations of the legislative process and its directions. In particular, Kh.Odilkoriev and U.Mukhamedov put forward a proposal to adopt a Code of the Legislative Process, in which all legislative acts in the legislative process will be systematized, sorted, revised [8].

It is known that legal expertise plays an important role in preventing conflicts in legislation. Unfortunately, there is no single legislative act in our country aimed at comprehensively regulating relations in the field of legal expertise of draft legislative acts. In this regard, it is necessary to adopt the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Legal Expertise of Regulatory Legal Acts," aimed at covering the entire mechanism of legal expertise of legislative acts. At the same time, an important factor in identifying conflicts in current legislation is the regular inventory of regulatory legal acts, monitoring their implementation, and, on this basis, submitting relevant proposals and recommendations to the subjects of lawmaking.

Moreover, legislative monitoring of conflict situations, carried out on the basis of specific experience, should include the most rational ways to resolve typical legal conflicts and those that meet the interests of all participants in legal relations. Consequently, legislative monitoring, carried out in various spheres of public life, reveals methods for ensuring the legality of the

behavior of legal entities. In this regard, we consider it expedient to adopt the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Procedure for Conducting Monitoring of Legislative Acts," covering all aspects of the implementation of monitoring of legislative acts.

Consequently, the systematic improvement of the legal foundations and mechanisms for resolving legal conflicts in our country serves as an important factor in the formation of a perfect legal system and ensuring the supremacy of the constitution and law, strengthening legality and law and order.

Conclusion. Based on the foregoing, it can be said that the systematization and harmonization of legislation plays an important role in eliminating legal conflicts in legislation. Systematization methods, such as codification and consolidation, help to reduce contradictions between legislative acts. At the same time, systematic approaches are necessary to eliminate duplication and inconsistencies arising in the legislative process. This will serve to improve the quality of legislation and strengthen the rule of law.

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